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Research Article

**ANXIETY PROPORTION AND ITS RELATED CONDITION IN
ALMAAREFA COLLEGE IN RIYADH, KSA DURING 2014-2015.**¹Abrar Al bishri, ²Aminah al Essa, ³BatoolAlherz, ⁴Ebtehalhamid, ⁵Fatimah Alabdulmohsen, ⁶GhadaAlkhahtani, ⁷HawraAlabbad, ⁸Lubna Abdullah, ⁹MahaAlashmouny, ¹⁰Noor Alaithan.¹Department of research, almaarefa college Riyadh, Saudi Arabia.**Abstract:**

Anxiety is a general term for several disorders that cause nervousness, fear, apprehension, and worrying. It is very important condition to spot the light on since it's widely spread in worldwide - the most common of all mental disorders—currently affects about one in 13 people [Baxter A., 2012] - regardless age, and depending on its severity, its effect varies from person to person. We distributed our questionnaire to the students of Al-Maarifa college in Riyadh during November 2015. In 12/12/2015 we received 139 replied (responders) through e-mail, WhatsApp, face book and line Apps.

The collected data were analyzed using IBM SPSS version 20 program. For analysis purpose, sex, faculty, and anxiety score were coded. Mean and standard deviation values of age, and anxiety score were calculated. In this research, among the all students, 75.5% of students are suffering from anxiety.

Moreover, it was concluded that the prevalence of anxiety in Faculty of medicine (69.1%) was the highest among other Faculties. Furthermore, anxiety levels were found to be highest in junior students.

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INTRODUCTION:

Anxiety is a general term for several disorders that cause nervousness, fear, apprehension, and worrying. It is very important condition to spot the light on since it's widely spread in worldwide - the most common of all mental disorders—currently affects about one in 13 people [Baxter A., 2012] - regardless age, and depending on its severity, its effect varies from person to person.

College students, especially females [Farooqi Y., 2012] are prone to anxiety more than males [Szűcs D., 2012], the reasons for these gender differences may be due to that women tend to be more involved in personal relationships than men and suffer more when they are disrupted, which might be due to hormonal and brain chemistry differences. Academic anxiety among students have long been researched on, and researchers have identified stressors as family expectations and fear of failure [Bataineh M., 2013], financial [Andrews B., 2004] or other difficulties [Abdulghani H., 2008], [Väfors M., 2008] and institutional difficulties [Elgilany A., 2008] that could increase the students' levels of anxiety, and might affect their academic performance either positively [Owens M., 2012] or negatively [Sohail N., 2010], [Singh S.,2009], [Syokwaa K., 2014], if not well managed [Al-Anzi F., 2005].

Previous researches had not concentrate on saudicollegejunior or senior students (Elgilany A., 2008), (Hashmat S., 2008), (Bataineh M., 2013),not covered gender factor (ginawi I., 2014), not covered students achievements in college (Syokwaa K., 2014), (Owens M., 2012).

In this research we are going to check proportion of anxiety among students of Almaarefa colleges at different colleges, to see if gender, age, home conditions and college environment affects anxiety level, and the impact of anxiety on students' academic achievements.

There is many difficulties that might face us in this research such as there is no specific definition for anxiety, cross sectional design its self and as we are doing the study in small faculty we may not have enough students with anxiety (small sample size) covering specific ages. The purpose of this research lies in how it helps in reducing the stressors not only for the students but for anyone who might be have anxiety and by that it helps in Raising the academic GPA.

OBJECTIVES:❖ **General objective:**

. To identify the proportion and associated risk factors of the anxiety among Al Maarifa students during 2014-2015.

❖ **Specific objectives:**

- 1- To assess proportion of anxiety, any differences in this proportion between male & female/junior & senior students.
- 2- To identify any link between the anxiety and home conditions (finance, marital status, family size etc.)
- 3- To verify relation between anxiety and student achievements
- 4- To assess any relation between anxiety and the college environment (Time constraints, the curriculum, entertainments, transport etc.)

RESEARCH QUESTION:

- 1- how To assess proportion of anxiety, any differences in this proportion between male & female/junior & senior students.?
- 2- what is the link between the anxiety and home conditions (finance, marital status, family size etc.)?
- 3- how To verify relation between anxiety and student achievements?
- 4- is there any relation between anxiety and the college environment (Time constraints, the curriculum, entertainments, transport?)

HYPOTHESIS:

In this research, we suggest:

- i) younger students (lower levels) are experiencing higher levels of anxiety than older ones.
- ii) female students are more anxious than males.
- iii) students of medical college are more anxious than students of other colleges.
- iv) married students (males / females) have higher anxiety levels than unmarried students of same level.

The reason that we choose this topic is because anxiety is a real phenomenon. And due to its important significance at all levels of life it plays a crucial role in human life because all of us are the victims of anxiety in different ways (**academic, medical, Social, Personal life**).

LITERATURE REVIEWS:

Abdulhady Elgilany. Perceived stress among male medical students in Egypt and Saudi Arabia: effect of sociodemographic factors at Mansoura University, Egypt and King Faisal University, Saudi Arabia. 2008. Study found that Egyptian students were more likely to cite relationship , academic and environmental problems than Saudis, anxiety and depression were significantly higher among Egyptian than Saudi students. A logistic regression analysis of

independent predictors of severe stress among both groups combined revealed that a satisfactory family income and university-graduated father were independent protective factors. The independent risk predictors were anxiety and number of stressors.

Bernice Andrews. The Relation of Depression and Anxiety to Life-Stress and Achievement in Students.UK, 2004. Results showed that by mid-course 9% of previously symptom-free students became depressed and 20% became anxious at a clinically significant level. Of those previously anxious or depressed 36% had recovered. After adjusting for pre-entry symptoms, financial difficulties made a significant independent contribution to depression and relationship difficulties independently predicted anxiety. Depression and financial difficulties mid-course predicted a decrease in exam performance from first to second year.

DénesSzűcs. Gender difference in mathematics anxiety and the relation to mathematics performance (MA) while controlling for test anxiety at University of Cambridge, UK. 2012. The study revealed that there is no gender differences emerged for mathematics performance but levels of MA and TA (test anxiety) were higher for girls than for boys. Moreover, girls and boys showed a positive correlation between MA and TA and a negative correlation between MA and mathematics performance. The TA was also negatively correlated with mathematics performance , but this relationship was stronger for girls than for boys. When controlling for TA, the negative correlation between MA and performance remained for girls only. Furthermore, the regression analyses revealed that MA was a significant predictor of performance for girls but not for boy. Similar studies were also relating anxiety to home \ work conditions.

FreihOwayed El-Anzi. Academic Achievement and Its Relationship with Anxiety, Self-Esteem, Optimism and Pessimism in Kuwaiti Students. 2005, the Basic Education College in Kuwait. Resulted in that there was a significant positive correlation between academic achievement and both optimism and self-esteem – whereas the correlations were negative between academic achievement and both anxiety and pessimism.

Hamza Mohammad Abdulghani. Stress and depression among medical students: A cross sectional study at a medical college in Saudi Arabia. KSU, KSA. 2008. The study found that the main source of stress found to be their studies (60.3%), followed by

home environment (2.8%) and 36.9% of study population did not mention any source of stress.

Jadoon N. Anxiety and Depression among Medical Students: a Cross-Sectional Study. Nishtar Medical College, Multan. 2008. They found that age, marital status, locality and total family income did not significantly affect the prevalence of anxiety and depression.

KaulaAssumptaSyokwaa. The Relationship between Anxiety Levels and Academic Achievement among Students in Selected Secondary Schools in Lang'ata District, Kenya. 2014. The study found out that, there was a correlation between anxiety levels and academic achievement, and that high anxiety levels had a negative impact on the quality of academic results recorded by students. The study also established that students' encountered some high anxiety causing challenges which affect their ability to perform effectively, and girls were found to be more prone to high anxiety levels as compared to boys. The study recommended that, students should take responsibility to seek for anxiety management help from teacher counselors, other teachers.

Marie Väfors. Stressors, anxiety, acculturation and adjustment among international and North American students. ethnically diverse community college in Southern California, United States. 2008. Results showed no significant differences were found between international students and students with permanent US residency. However, when the international student population was sub-grouped by above cultural regions a different pattern emerged. Difficulties of not being able to work and of socially related problems were perceived as more severe for the European and the Asian groups, while finance problems were hard for all three groups. The variable of language difficulties was harder for Asian students, while that of stress of being apart from family was harder for students from Europe.

Marwan Z. Bataineh. Academic Stress Among Undergraduate Students: The Case of Education Faculty at King Saud University. 2013. The result showed that academic overloads, course awkward, inadequate time to study, workload every semester, exams awkward, low motivation, and high family expectations were drive moderately stress among students. It was also found that fear of failure is the major source of stress among undergraduate students. The study also revealed that there were no significant differences in academic stress among students with different, level of study and specializations.

Matthew Owens. Exam anxiety may lead to better grades. At the British Journal of Psychology, UK. 2012. The results provided that when working memory was poor, increased anxiety was associated with low test scores. When working memory was good, anxiety was associated with higher test results. It highlights that anywhere between 10 percent and 40 percent of children are affected by anxiety around taking tests, support offered in schools could be targeted in the first instance to those who are at higher risk of poor outcomes. On the other hand, many studies had linked between environmental stressors and anxiety levels.

NudratSohail. Stress and Academic Performance Among Medical Students in AllamaIqbal Medical College, Lahore. 2010. This study illustrated the presence of a moderate, negative and significant relationship between sources of stress, levels of stress on the academic performance of a student. The study also showed a diversity of stress sources and a high level of stress in the medical students and showed that higher level of stress is associated with poor academic performance.

Singh S. The role of Anxiety in achievement. Punjab, India. 2009. The results reported that there exists a negative and significant relationship between anxiety and achievement. Significant differences were observed between boys and girls, rural and urban students on the basis of their anxiety.

YasminNiloferFarooqi. Gender Differences in Test Anxiety and Academic Performance of Medical Students. University of the Punjab, New Campus, Lahore, Pakistan. 2012. The results suggested that the female medical students reported significantly higher

test anxiety level as compared to the male medical students. Moreover, the results suggested that the male medical students achieved statistically significant higher GPAs as compared to the female medical students. Furthermore, significant negative relationship was found between test anxiety and academic performance of medical students.

METHODOLOGY:

A-Approach

- ❖ **Study design:** a descriptive observational cross sectional study
- ❖ **Study area:** Almaarefa College in Riyadh, KSA during 2014-2015.
- ❖ **Study population:**
Population is from 5 different colleges (medicine, nursing, computer sciences, applied sciences and respiratory care), males and females. 2015-2016
- ❖ **Sample size:** 250 students (males/females) are included.
- ❖ **Describe the baseline demographic characteristics of the sample**
 - Males and Females.
 - Different colleges.
 - Different levels.
 - Age group (19-25).
 - Different nationalities.
- ❖ **Specify Inclusion/Exclusion criteria**

Inclusion	Exclusion
Students are from different colleges and levels	Students with organic pathology, physical or psychotic illnesses are excluded.
Married / unmarried	Students on medications are excluded.
Age :17-25	
Male/ female	
Different Nationalities	

- ❖ **Time: April/2015**
- ❖ **B-Data needs**
- ❖ **Measures & Instruments:**
 - end closed questions – questionnaire.
- ❖ **Describe the type of instrument being used:**

Beck Anxiety Inventory has a cutoff score of 8, with the range of 8-15 for mild anxiety, 16-25 for moderate anxiety and 26-63 for severe anxiety.

- ❖ **Describe how you will address Reliability & Validity of instruments/measures.:**
We going to check the reliability and validity of our research by applying a pilot study.

❖ Variables

Sort of Variable	Variable	Type
Independent variables	Anxiety	Levels – continuous
Dependent variables	Academic achievement	Poor vs. high – dichotomous
Moderating (background)	DEMOGRAPHY	
	Gender	Frequency of meals/day – discrete
	Age	Continuous
	Nationality	Discrete
	Marital status	Yes/No – dichotomous
	Study levels	years – discrete
	College	M\RH\Ph\Comp\ER – Discrete
	SOCIO.ECONOMIC STATUS	
	Income	High \ Moderate \ Low – discrete
	Mother education	
	Father education	
	Family members	
	Working status	Yes\no -
	Residency	
	PERSONAL	
	Work with people you don't know	
	Troubles with partners	
	Troubles with classmates	
	Sleep hours	Continuous
	ACADEMIC	
	Classes work load	
	Missing classes	
	Troubles with instructors	
	Lower grades than anticipated	
	Exams frequency	How many per week\month – discrete
	Curriculum	Full semester \ integrated blocks – dichotomous
	ENVIRONMENTAL	
	Computer problems	
	Luxury time	Continuous
	Transport	Bus\ private – dichotomous
	Living condition	Messy\organized

❖ Design the Questionnaire.

QUESTIONNAIRE:

If you are interested in finding out the severity of your anxiety, you can complete the following anxiety questionnaire. Your responses on this anxiety questionnaire are confidential. This test provides a rough estimate of how much anxiety you have and it should not be used for a diagnosis. On this page is a list of behaviors that may or may not be relevant for you. Based on your personal experience, please indicate how frequently you experience these feelings and thoughts in social situations.

Anxiety

Address:.....

City, state, zip:

.....

Sex: Female Male

1-How old are you? -----

2- gender:

A-Male

B- female.

3- What is the Study level? -----

4- How many members in your family? -----

5-What is a level of your Income?

A-High

b-Moderate

C-Low – discrete

6-are you married?

A-Yes

b-No

7-Do you have children? If yes how many are they?

A-Yes

b-No

8-I worry about what my parents will say?

a-all the time

B-Nearly every day

C-More than half the days

D-Several days

E-Not at all

9-College: a-Medicine

B-Pharmacy

C-Respiratory care

D-Computer sciences

E-Nursing

F-Information system

G-Emergency medical service

10- How many Exams frequency you get? -----

11-I have less difficulty than the average college student in learning assigned chapters in textbooks?

A-Yes

b-No

12-I am calmer in test situations than the average college student?

A-Yes

b-No

13-It is hard for me to remember the answers in my exams?

A-Yes

b-No

14-I feel under a lot of pressure to get good grades on tests?

A-Yes

b-No

15-When I take a test, my nervousness causes me to make careless errors

.a-Yes

b-No

16-How often do you miss classes? A-Usuallyb-Neverc-I rarely attend-Sometimes

17- Do you get Lower grades than anticipated?

A-Yes

b-No

18-the number of working hours-----

19-How often do you have days off? -----

20-Curriculum:

A-Full semester

B-Integrated body system blocks

21-I have less interest in activities that I normally enjoyed?

A-Yes

b-No

22-What type of transport do you use?

A-Bus

B-private – dichotomous

23-I am afraid of crowds, being left alone, the dark, of strangers, or of traffic

A-Yes

No

b-

Working Together We Can:

Build Student Confidence...Improve Test Performance...Promote Our Most Anxious Students

❖ **Data analysis (How data will be analyze?)**

We are going to follow the steps:

- 1- clearance
- 2- coding
- 3- entering
- 4- suitable statistic will be done to obtain the frequency and percentage

❖ **How will be presented? (dummy tables)**

DEMOGRAPHY	
Gender	
Age	
Nationality	
Marital status	
Study levels	
College	

SOCIO.ECONOMIC STATUS	
Income	
Mother education	
Father education	
Family members	
Working status	
Residency	

PERSONAL	
Work with people you don't know	
Troubles with partners	
Troubles with classmates	
Sleep hours	

ACADEMIC	
Classes work load	
Missing classes	
Troubles with instructors	
Lower grades than anticipated	
Exams frequency	
Curriculum	

ENVIRONMENTAL	
Computer problems	
Luxury time	
Transport	
Living condition	

❖ **Statistical test be used**❖ **Ethical consideration.**

Obtain an informed consent

Gain college consent

Respect conventionality

Keep anonymous

RESULT:

We distributed our questionnaire to the students of Al-Maarifa college in Riyadh during November 2015. In 12/12/2015 we received 139 replied (responders) through e-mail, WhatsApp, face book and line Apps.

The collected data were analyzed using IBM SPSS version 20 program. For analysis purpose, sex, faculty, and anxiety score were coded. Mean and standard deviation values of age, and anxiety score were calculated.

The cut-off score used for anxiety using GAD was 5-10-15.

Table 1: Sociodemographic characteristics of ANXIETY student, Chi-square to find the significant level ($p=0.05$) with gender (total number of $n=139$)

Variable	No	%	P-value
Gender			
Male	47	33.8	
Female	92	66.2	
Age			0.61
30-26	4	2.9	
25-21	93	66.9	
20-17	42	30.2	
Nationality			0.07
Saudi	110	79.1	
Non-Saudi	29	20.9	

- Majority of responders were females (92), while males (47).
- Majority of responders were between age of 21-25 (93), then (42) were between age of 17-20, and very few between age of 26-30 (4).
- Most responders were Saudis, 110 responders (79.1%), while non Saudis were 29 responders (20.9%).

Table 2: (college & level distribution):

Variable	No	%
College		
Medicine	96	69.1
Clinical pharmacy	19	13.7
Respiratory therapy	19	13.7
Nursing	2	1.4
Emergency medicine	2	1.4
Information system	1	0.7
Study level		
3 th	29	20.9
4 th	17	12.2
5 th	21	15.1
6 th	13	9.4
7 th	28	20.1

8 th	16	11.5
9 th	7	5
10 th	1	0.7
11 th	3	2.2
12 th	1	0.7

- Most responders were from college of medicine (96) out of which (63) females and (33) males.
- Respiratory care responders were (19), 4 males and 15 females.
- Pharmacy students' responders were (18), 11 females and 7 males.
- Emergency department (2) males.
- Nursing (2) males.
- Only (1) female responded from college of computer science.

- Most responders were from college of medicine (96), respiratory care (19), pharmacy (18), emergency department (2), nursing (2) and only (1) computer science.
- Majority of responders were 29 at L.3 (20.9%), 28 at L.7 (20.1%), 21 at L.5 (15.1%), 17 at L.4 (12.2), 16 at L.8 (11.5%).

Table 3: Distribution of medical students studied according to age, sex, anxiety and depression levels.

Variable	No	%
Age		
Sex		
Male	47	33.8
Female	92	66.2
Anxiety		
Mild anxiety	8	13
Moderate anxiety	25	18
Severe anxiety	72	51.8

The relation between over all , anxiety level and others variables.

According to GAD anxiety test cut-off points mentioned in our proposal;

- Out of 92 female responder, 71(77.17%) were suffering from anxiety.
- Out of 47 male responders, 34 (72.34%) suffers from anxiety.

Males; 47

- 33 (70.2%) of male responders were from college of medicine, out of which 25 (75.8%)suffers from anxiety.
- 7 (14.9%) responders from college of pharmacy, out of which 4 (57.1%) suffers from anxiety.
- 4 (8.5%) responders from college of respiratory care, out of which 3 (75%) were found to suffer from anxiety.

Table 4: Male Students Anxiety Level for college prospective.

Variable	No	Anxiety Level				
		Extremly severe n(%)	Severe n(%)	Moderate n(%)	Mild n(%)	Normal n(%)
college						
Medicine	33	3(9)	14(42.4)	4(12.1)	4(12.1)	8(24.2)
Pharmacy	7	0(0)	2(28.5)	0(0)	2(28.5)	3(42.8)
Respiratory therapi	4	0(0)	2(50)	1(25)	0(0)	1(25)
Nursing	0	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)

Clinical pharmacy	0	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)
Emergency medicine	2	0(0)	1(50)	0(0)	0(0)	1(50)
Information system	1	0(0)	1(100)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)

Females; 92

- 63 (67.7%) responders were from college of medicine, out of which 47 (74.6%) suffers from anxiety.
- 15 (16.1%) of respiratory care college responded, out of which 12 (80%) suffers from anxiety.
- 12 (12.9%) responders from college of pharmacy, out of which 10 (83.3%) suffers from anxiety.

Table 5: Female Students Anxiety Level for college prospective.

variable	No	Anxiety Level				
		Extremely severe n(%)	Severe n(%)	Moderate n(%)	Mild n(%)	Normal n(%)
College						
Medicine	63	4(6.3)	27(42.8)	14(22.3)	2(3.1)	16(25.3)
Pharmacy	11	0(0)	6(54.5)	3(27.2)	0(0)	2(18.1)
Respiratory therapy	15	2(13.4)	9(60)	1(6.7)	0(0)	3(20)
Nursing	2	0(0)	1(50)	1(50)	0(0)	0(0)
Clinical pharmacy	1	0(0)	0(0)	1(100)	0(0)	0(0)
Emergency medicine	0	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)
Information system	0		0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)

-
- 93 of responders falls between the age of 21-25, out of which 67 (72%) were found to be suffering from anxiety.
 - 42 responders falls between the age of 17-20, out of which 35 (83.3%) suffers from anxiety.
 - 4 of responders were between age of 26-30, 2 (50%) of them suffers from anxiety.

-
- 128 of responders are singles, out of which 96 (75%) are anxious.
 - 9 responders are married, 7 (77.8%) were anxious. while only 2 responders were divorced and were found to be anxious.

-
- 73 responders (52.5%) have 6-8hours sleep per day. out of which 50 (68.5%) suffers from anxiety.
 - Students having irregular sleeping patterns were 32 (23%) of responders, 27 (84.3%) of them suffers from anxiety.
 - Students having less than 5hours of sleeping daily were 26 (18.7%), 24 (92.3%) of them suffers from anxiety.
 - Students sleeping more than 8 hours daily were 8 (5.7%) of responders, 4 (50%) of them were found to suffer from anxiety.

-
- Most responders "53 of 139" (38%) think their academic performance is v.good, out of which 34 (64.2%) suffers from anxiety.
 - 47 (33.8%) responders think their performance is good, 39 (83%) of them suffers from anxiety.
 - 20 (14.4%) responders think their performance is excellent, 15 (75%) of them suffers from anxiety.
 - 19 (13.7%) responders think their performance is weak, 17 (89.5%) of them suffers from anxiety.
-

- Out of 139 responders, 14 had a low family income, 13 (92.9%) of them suffers from anxiety.
- Majority (61) have a high family income, out of which 43 (70.5%) suffers from anxiety.
- 45 responders didn't know how much is there family income, 33 (73.3%) of them suffers from anxiety.
- 19 responders have a moderate family income, out of which 16(84.21%) are anxious.
-
- The vast majority of responders (131) are unemployed. out of them, 98 (74.8%) were found to be anxious.
- 8 responders are employees, 7 (87.5%) of them are anxious.
-
- 127 responders having (Family, Financial, Transport, examination results, and home duties problems), 93 (73.22%) suffers from anxiety.
- 4 responders have academic pressure, all of them (100%) were found to be anxious.
- 4 finds high family expectations increases their anxiety level, all of them (100) found to be anxious.

Table.6: Summarizing table showing the distribution of studied students according to age, sex, anxiety and depression levels for each faculty.

Variable	Number	%
<i>Age</i>		
17-20	42	30.2
21-25	93	66.9
26-30	4	0.61
<i>Sex</i>		
Male	47	33.8
Female	92	66.2
<i>Faculty</i>		
Medicine	96	69.1
Pharmacy	18	12.9
<i>Anxiety state</i>		
Mild anxiety	8	13
Moderate anxiety	25	18
Severe anxiety	72	51.8

DISCUSSION:

In this research, among the all students, 75.5% of students are suffering from anxiety. Moreover, it was concluded that the prevalence of anxiety in Faculty of medicine (69.1%) was the highest among other Faculties. Furthermore, anxiety levels were found to be highest in junior students. Several theories were explained in many researches. Some have relied these findings to their studies [Abdulghani H.,2008]. Medical students pass through continuous examinations throughout their academic years ,Studying medicine is competitive. And so, they are more worried about the results [Andrews B., 2004]. Not many studies supported our finding regarding junior vs. senior students. However, other studies showed that there is no different between anxiety levels among different majorities and levels of students [Bataineh M., 2013].

Our study revealed that there are differences in anxiety symptoms between genders. The prevalence of the symptoms was higher among females. Different studies showed similarity with our study in reporting higher levels of anxiety among females. [Farooqi Y., 2012], [Szűcs D., 2012].

In this study, we also found that home conditions and total family income was a big contributor in students levels of anxiety (62%). Similarity with other researches was also found [Abdulghani H., 2008]. But other studies showed contrariety to our results [Jandoon N., 2008].

In our study, we found that levels of anxiety were higher in married and employed students. Not many studies supports this theory, but some showed

CONCLUSION:

Our result shows variability in the cause of anxiety so do our recommendations, as the important step to resolve any problem starts with education the students, they should be more aware about the hazards and complication of anxiety this can be done in “activity day “ provided by the collage it self.

As the collage plays major roll in student life it also should have play a roll in helping student’s to control their emotions “specially during exams “ and anxiety, the students spent most of their time in the collage so they need intermittent space where they can share their talents, as the collage already Provided a consultant for the students but this alone is not enough, also during the class the professors can use other than the traditional way in teaching and delivering the information to the student, this can have very good benefits to the collage by increasing

contrariety to this [Jandoon N., 2008]. Further studies are needed to consider marital status and work difficulties one of stressors among college students.

In this research, although wasn't taken to a big consideration, but it was found that students with higher levels of anxiety complains of low academic achievement. That finding is supported by many previous studies [Sohail N., 2010], [Singh S.,2009], that anxiety negatively affects academic achievement [Syokwaa K., 2014], if not well managed [Al-Anzi F., 2005]. Other studies were found to be contrary to this [Owens M., 2012] suggesting that the more anxious the student is, the better academic performance he/she does.

In this study, some limitations should be considered. One of those limitations is possibility of biased sampling because questionnaire was distributed to more female students than males, more to medical students than other colleges, and even to more certain levels than others. Generalizing our results to all Riyadh medical students is hard because students were drawn from just one university in Riyadh. The second point is that family history of stressful events was not taken into consideration. Further studies should take these limitations including genetic and environmental problems into consideration. Another point is this study didn't take academic achievement in a big consideration, it was more towards finding the types of stressors.

Lastly, not enough sample size was selected, so larger sample size should be considered in future studies.

the outcome in high quality and very well educated students.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

Our result shows variability in the cause of anxiety so do our recommendations, as the important step to resolve any problem starts with education the students, they should be more aware about the hazards and complication of anxiety this can be done in “activity day“ provided by the collage it self.

As the collage plays major roll in student life it also should have play a roll in helping student’s to control their emotions “specially during exams “ and anxiety, the students spent most of their time in the collage so they need intermittent space where they can share their talents, as the collage already Provided a consultant for the students but this alone is not enough, also during the class the professors can use

other than the traditional way in teaching and delivering the information to the student, this can have very good benefits to the collage by increasing the outcome in high quality and very well educated students.

All what is mentioned above can be easily done with minimum losses ,But as our study where done on small sample So, further studies with more sample size using multivariate techniques are to be planned .

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QUESTIONNAIRE

Personal Information :-

1.Gender:

Male
female

2. Age :

- 20-17
 25-21
 30-26
 Other:

3.Nationality:

4.Marital status:

Single

- Married
absolute
 Widower
Other:

5.mijor :

6.Study level:

Preparatoryyear (I - II)

- Third
the fourth
 Other:

7.family income per month:

- Lessthan 3,000RS
 3000 - 6000
 6000 - 9000
 More than 9,000
 I do not know

8.fathers level ofeducation :

Less thanhigh school

- Secondary Education
college degree
 higher studies

9.mothers level ofeducation :

- Less thanhigh school
 Secondary Education
college degree
 higher studies

10. family members are :

- Less than 3 members
- Of 3-5 members
- 6-10 members
- More than 10

11. your job :

- I do not work
- I work part-time
- I work full time
- Other:

12. permanent place of residence:

- Central Region
- Eastern Province
- Western Area
- North side
- Other:

13. Where do you live currently:

- With Parents
- in special residence
- Student housing

14. Transportation:

- private car
- Bus
- Other:

Please answer the following questions:-*

15. In general, how do you find your academic achievement?

- Weak
- Good
- very good
- Excellent

16. In general, do you see that you meet your parents expectations about your academic achievement?

- Yes
- Sometimes
- No

17. In general, how would you describe the level of tension you have?

- Weak
- Average

- natural
- High
- exaggerated

18. In general, describe your life as:

- organization
- Moderate
- unorganized

19. How long is your school day?

- 2-5 hours
- 6-8 hours
- More than 8 hours

20. How many your Weekly Restdays?

- There is no
- one day
- Two days
- More than two days

21. The average number of hours you sleep per day:

- Less than 5 hours
- From 6-8 hours
- More than 8 hours
- irregular

22. Number of hours of entertainment per week:

- Less than 7 hours
- 10-7 hours
- More than 10 hours

The following questions..If you answered "yes" select the "other", and mention it please. *

23. Do you suffer from a chronic disease?

- No
- Other:

24. Do you follow a treatment for a disease?

- No
- Other:

25. The following, what do you think it raises the level of tension you have? *
(You can choose more than one answer to determine its own option)

- Family problems
- Financial problems
- High expectations of parents
- transportation problems

Softwareproblems
Increaseacademic load
Absence fromlectures
The test results
Many of the tasksand homework
Workingwithin a groupyou do not know
Lecturersuncooperative
uncomfortable class rooms
Other: